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Research Article

Dynamics of Land use/land cover in Kahuwa River Micro-catchment in Response to Urbanization from 1986 to 2010

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the change in land use/ cover in Kahuwa micro-catchment from 1986 to 2010. Landsat images covering three periods 1986, 2000 and 2010 were analyzed using unsupervised classification in ILWIS 3.3 software. Past land-use/cover was reconstructed using key informant interviews as well as existing land-use/cover maps of the area (such as the GLC2000 and the Africover maps). The result showed five major land use/cover types including forest, grassland, built-up areas, open water and small-scale farmlands. Between 1986 and 2000, the forest area decreased by 7.14% at the rate of 135.39 ha for the considered period and between 2000 and 2010, the forest decrease was also about 141.04 ha. The increase in the built-up area has led to a number of environmental and ecological problems. Proper land use planning is essential for sustainable development of Kahuwa river micro-catchment.

Keywords: land use/land cover, dynamics, urbanization, environment, Kahuwa river micro-catchment, D.R. Congo.

INTRODUCTION

Land use and land cover are known to strongly increase due to the acceleration of the global urbanization (Carlson and Arthur, 2000; Sajjad and Iqbal, 2012). There is a growing interest in understanding its implication in the broad set of environmental factors such as decline water quality, natural vegetation and climate at local, regional and global scale (Turner *et al.*, 1994; Grimn *et al.*, 2000; Lopez *et al.*, 2001; Alphan, 2003; Mahan *et al.*, 2011). Land use and land cover information is important for several planning and management activities related to earth surface. It constitutes key environmental information for many scientists, resource managers and policy makers, as well as for a range of human activities. It has become a central component in current strategies of natural resource management and monitoring environmental changes (Bhagawat, 2011; Zhou and Wang, 2011). The importance of land use and land cover has been emphasized in many disciplines that link very important societal issues including global climatic change, food security, soil degradation, water pollution and biodiversity conservation (Turner II *et al.*, 1995; Lambin *et al.*, 2001; Geist and Lambin, 2002).

Changes in land use and land cover are defined broadly to include the conversion of lands into croplands and pastures, the abandonment of agricultural lands, deforestation, reforestation, shifting cultivation, and urban sprawl (Evrendilek, 2004; Evrendilek and Wali, 2004). In developing countries, where urbanization rates are high, urban sprawl is a significant contributor of the land use change (Dewan and Yamaguchi, 2009; Jat *et al.*, 2008; Mundia and Aniya, 2006; Yin *et al.*, 2011).

Sprawl generally refers to some type of uncoordinated development with impacts such as loss of agricultural land, open space and ecologically sensitive habitats in and around urban areas due to lack of integrated and holistic approaches in regional planning (Sudhira and Ramachandra, 2007; Mohan *et al.*, 2011). Urban growth is occurring at an unprecedented rate worldwide with 65% of the population expected to reside in urban areas by 2025 (Schell and Uljaszek, 1999). Natural population increase and migration of people from rural to urban areas are two main factors contributing to rapid urban growth (Dewan and Yamaguchi 2009; Sajjad and Iqbal, 2012). This process has, however, caused many impacts on the environment and become a critical issue in global change research (NRC, 2001).

Identifying, delineating and mapping land use and land cover types, hence, are important activities in support of sustainable natural resource management. Subsequent effect of land use/ land cover changes, include among others increased pollution, forest fragmentation, losses of productive lands and biodiversity. This is increasingly threatening ecosystem productivity and health on the local, regional and global scales (Wali *et al.*, 1999; Evrendilek and Ertekin, 2002; Evrendilek, 2004; Bhagawat, 2011). In the last few decades, numerous examples of decreasing water quantity, quality and disappearing of freshwater lakes and rivers have been reported across the world (Gorsevski, 2008). One of the famous cases includes the disappearance of Lake Chad, located in Africa, linked to recent climatic events and intensified agricultural practices. The lake has decreased significantly in the past 35 years to 1/20th of its original size (Gorsevski, 2008). There are many similar examples at different spatio-temporal scales that have been recorded in the past few decades (Bhagawat, 2011). There is need, however, to identify the nature of the changes, where and when they occur, the rates at which they occur, the social and physical forces that drive those changes, and to understand the effect of these changes on environmental systems (Lambin *et al.*, 2003; Munns, 2006; Dale *et al.*, 2008). It is therefore very important to estimate the rate, pattern and type of land use and land cover changes in order to predict future changes in urban development (Dewan and Yamaguchi, 2009; Molan *et al.*, 2011). In the Kahuwa river micro-catchment in Bukavu city, no comprehensive study on the dynamics of land use land cover change has so far been done. The rapid rate of urban expansion due to a rise in population migrated from insecure areas in rural part of the province coupled with economic growth is causing land use/land cover changes in Kahuwa river micro-catchment of Bukavu city. Serious environmental problems have been noticed in the micro-catchment as a result of rapid urban development. If the present trend continues, it will certainly lead to severe degradation of natural resources of the micro-catchment, hence it calls for a proper land use policy.

Thus, this study attempts to analyze land use and land cover change in Kahuwa river micro-catchment using satellite images of 1986, 2000 and 2010, so that sustainable land use and eco-environmental restoration planning can be formulated by policy makers.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Description of the study area

Kahuwa River micro-catchment is one of the areas of the Bukavu city on the southern flank of Lake Kivu in Democratic Republic of the Congo (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Kahuwa river micro-catchment in Bukavu city.

It is located between latitudes 2°29' – 2°33'S and longitudes 28°48' – 28°52'E, at an altitude between 1500 and 2194 m asl. The 19.19 Km² micro-catchment, covering 31% of the Bukavu City, is bordered by Lake Kivu in the north, by the Tshula River micro-catchment in the west and by Ruzizi River catchment in the east. Kahuwa River micro-catchment is located in the urban centre of Bukavu City and with a medium to high density areas (9.10³ hab./Km²) (Muvundja *et al.*, 2009). The micro-catchment geomorphologic history is closely similar to that of the African Grabben, which is appertained precisely to Western Rift Valley, a result of high tectonic activity which had put in place the spectacular and rough relief characterizing the area and responsible for soil erosion and landslides in Bukavu region (Moeyersons *et al.*, 2004). The soil of Bukavu is dominantly ferralsol susceptible to high rate of erosion when exposed (Moeyersons *et al.*, 2004). The climate is tropical humid type influenced by the trade winds. The latitude and the altitude are the principal factors that determine the climate of Bukavu. It is hilly with two seasons, three months of dry season, from June to August and nine months of rainy season, from

September to May. The average annual temperature and precipitation are 19°C and 1403 mm respectively (Bisimwa, 2009; Spigel and Coulter, 1996). The maximum temperature during the year is observed in August (~21°C) and rainfall in November (~220 mm).

Satellite image classification

Land-use/cover change was determined by analyzing a series of historical landsat satellite images. The satellite images covering the study area for different dates 1986, 2000 and 2010 were considered for this study. The DEM of 30m by 30m resolution was used to delineate the micro-catchment as recommended by other researches (Bingner, 1996; Sharma *et al.*, 1996; Tiwari *et al.*, 1997; Wang and Hjelmfelt, 1998). These satellite images were imported in Integrated Land and Water Information System (ILWIS) software version 3.3 for analysis. The images were clustered using unsupervised classification. Preliminary maps were validated using field observations and existing land-use/cover maps of the area (such as the GLC2000 and the Africover maps). Past land-use/cover was reconstructed using key informant interviews. The classification system utilized in this study is a slightly modified classification system for remotely sensed data as recommended by Anderson *et al.*, (1976). Visual interpretation of the images determines the land uses types. For simplicity because of the mixing classes in the area, three broad classification classes were used in the study: forest cover, cultivated/agriculture land and grassland and settlements/built-up area. The classes were recognized based on the character of the physiographic of the study area, scale/resolution (30 m) of the imageries used and the availability of ancillary information. Spatial data analysis was done in ILWIS 3.2 GIS software. Three pairs of Landsat images have been used to classify the study area (Landsat 1986, 2000 and 2010). All data used in this study were projected to the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projection system (Zone 35, World Geodetic System 84). The system then generates areas of each land use type. The dynamics of land use/cover was assessed by fitting a regression curve on the series of land use/ cover for the analyzed years.

RESULTS

Magnitude of land-use/cover changes

The image classification indicates that in 1986, cultivated/grassland (68.25 %) and forest (22.63 %) were the most predominant land-use/cover followed by built-up areas (9.12 %) (Table 1 and Figure 2). By year 2000, cultivated/grassland (75.02 %) and forest (15.99 %) remained the most predominant land-use/cover types followed by built-up areas (9.48 %) (Table 1 and Figure 2) but, there were reductions in land-use/cover types of forest and increase in cultivated/grassland and built-up areas (Table 1). In 2010, a significant change occurred in the area where built-up areas were known as the most predominant land-use/cover type (75.59 %) followed by forest (22.94 %) and cultivated/grassland (1.56 %). A significant reduction of cultivated/grassland was observed in the area.

Figure 2: Land use/land cover map of Kahuwa micro-catchment 1986, 2000 and 2010.

Table 1: Land use / land cover Areas for different years

Classes	1986		2000		2010	
	Hectares	%	Hectares	%	Hectares	%
Forest	432.72	22.63	297.33	15.49	438.37	22.84
Built-up area	181.26	9.12	181.98	9.48	1450.61	75.59
Grassland and small scale farmland	1305.2	68.25	1439.69	75.02	30.02	1.56
Total	1912.31	100	1919	100	1919	100

Changes analysis to provide insights into the spatial dynamics variation of land use/ cover patterns in different period of the study, analysis was performed and shows that Built-up area is the biggest contributor to the loss of cultivated/grassland area 66.11 % and forest 7.35 % in the Kahuwa river micro-catchment (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Dynamics of land use/land cover in the micro-catchment of river Kahuwa.

The loss of forest cover from 1986 to 2000 was apparent, and was followed by a slight increase from 2000 to 2010 due to probably an afforestation activity in the micro-catchment. We observed an increase of built-up areas in 2010 and a decrease of grassland and small-scale farmland in the same year.

DISCUSSION

The Kahuwa river micro-catchment classification indicates that the micro-catchment was characterized by three major land uses (cultivated/grasslands, forest and Built-up area) in the period between 1986 and 2010. However, there has been changes in the land use/cover systems in Kahuwa river micro-catchment. Cultivated/grasslands and forest land have reduced while built-up area have increased. Muvundja *et al.*, (2009) and Azanga *et al.*, (2012) have also shown significant land use/cover changes in Lake Kivu and Lake Tanganyika basins due to clearing of natural vegetation for cultivation, firewood and land fragmentation. Similar observations were made by Fazal et Amin, (2011) and Fazal, (2000), that the settlement represents the most profound alteration of the natural environment by people, through the imposition of structures, buildings, paved surfaces, and compacted bare soils on the ground surface.

Settlements also create demands that lead to other land-cover changes, such as the removal of vegetation and soil to extract sand, gravel, brick clays, and rock; the replacement of vegetation by planted cover in gardens, parks, sports grounds; the alienation of ground for landfill and waste treatment; wetlands and open space conversion for settlements and the use of land for transportation routes.

Between 1986 and 2000, an unchanged land use (Figure 6) can be noticed in built-up while a small increase in grassland and small-scale farm-land is observed and a decrease in forest cover is perceptible. The decrease in forests during the period 1986 to 2000 could be attributed to high demand of wood by the refugees from Rwanda. In this period a high demographic pressure occurred in the natural resources and was significant and the deforested area was used by the population for small scale farming in the micro-catchment because of rapid population growth rates and extensive soil erosion. This also corresponds to the findings of Geist and Lambin (2002) that agricultural expansion, overgrazing, charcoal burning and timber harvesting contributes 37% of land cover clearance which is one third of the causal factors for land cover depletion worldwide. Therefore it is noticed that both anthropogenic and natural drivers are the main cause of land use/cover change in similar regions (Obando *et al.*, 2007; Tiwari, 2008; Egeru *et al.*, 2009; Barasa *et al.*, 2010). From 2000 to 2010, a dramatic change is observed in the micro-catchment where the built-up areas increased dramatically.

The period 2000-2010 is characterized by dominant built-up areas which accounts for 66.11% (Figure 4), 7.35 % increase of the forest cover and the decrease of 73.46 % of grassland and small-scale farm-land area. Land use/cover change was very significant in Kahuwa river micro-catchment from 2000 to 2010. This increase of built-up areas are due to the political instability that characterized the country in that period which caused rural-urban migration in the Kahuwa micro-catchment. The green places and small scale farming were replaced by settlements. These areas were judged inappropriate to built-up by the municipality and the consequence is the erosion taking place in the micro-catchment. It was reported that Urban land-cover change is increasing dramatically in most developing nations (Attua and Fischer, 2011). In Africa and in the municipality of Ghana in particular, political stability and active socio-economic progress has pushed the urban frontier into the country side at the expense of the natural ecosystems at ever-increasing rates (Masek *et al.*, 2000 ; He *et al.*, 2008) .

The results in Shanghai metropolitan area (China) indicated that urbanization has accelerated at an unprecedented scale and rate land use, leading to a considerable reduction of farmland and grass land area (Yin *et al.*, 2011). In India, it was revealed that throughout the period of 1991–2010, the amount of built up area has increased dramatically whereas the area under agriculture has decreased drastically. The built-up areas experienced an increase of 5056 hectares while the areas under agriculture witnessed a decrease of 3241 hectares (Sajjad and Iqbal, 2012). The accelerated rate of expansion of the built up areas in Kahuwa river micro-catchment is attributed to repetitive wars in eastern D.R. Congo for over two decades and poor planning. The 1997 civil war and the insecurity which followed pushed many people out of their homes and part of the woodlots was then converted into agricultural land. In 2010, insecurity reduced in Bukavu town and its neighborhood but increased in the rural areas, many rural families found refuge in the periphery of the town where they built semi-permanent structures, with or without title deeds. Such rapid population growth in the micro-catchment of Kahuwa River has already exerted pressure on the existing land resources through increasing demand for food, wood for fuel as well as for construction purposes. This expansion of urban area in the micro-catchment has led to increased pollution of the Kahuwa River and the situation will worsen if appropriate measures are not put in place.

Population growth has long been considered a major factor leading to land-use change (Lin and Ho, 2003; Tanrivermis, 2003). In the Kahuwa river micro-catchment, we observed an increase of population and is generally seen as one of the most important factors of land-use change. A large amount of agricultural land has been converted to built-up or urban land uses to satisfy the high demand of resources of the population. This was also observed in other catchments as shown by many studies (Lamb, 1998; Loyn, 2000; Cawsey and Freudenberger, 2003; Kanowski *et al.*, 2003; Kanowski *et al.*, 2005; Koskela *et al.*, 2007).

Anthropogenic activities in Kahuwa river micro-catchment have brought deep changes in land use and land cover dynamics pattern, and is having a marked effect on ecosystem structure, function and dynamics; making the fragile Lake Kivu ecosystem polluted.

CONCLUSION

Land-use/cover had significantly changed in the Kahuwa micro-catchment. Built-up area increased by 66% and the grassland and small-scale farmland reduced up to 73%. The results of the dynamics of land use/cover pattern as revealed in this study provided a pointer to the need for all tiers of municipalities and government to put in place appropriate planning regulation to guide the direction of future growth and changes in the land use/cover in Kahuwa river micro-catchment.

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